

**METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING TEACHING OF THE SUBJECTS OF
"INFORMATION AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES" ON THE BASE OF
SOFTWARE TOOLS**

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Abstract

This article discusses the issues of creating multimedia presentations based on modern software tools and organizing lessons using them in the teaching of 5th grade "Informatics and Information Technologies" subjects in general secondary schools today.

Key words: Informatics and information technologies, working with a text document, software tool, electronic manual, hypertext, sound, graphics, video, test, multimedia, animation, simulation model, general secondary education, software tool.

Enter. In the 5th grade "Informatics and Information Technologies" subject in the secondary education schools, in the traditional educational method, the training sessions are mainly organized by the teacher on the basis of simple slides on the blackboard or video projector. With the help of computer tools and information technologies, it is possible to teach the subject of "Informatics and information technologies" to the students by demonstrating the educational materials with the help of models. The teaching of "Informatics and Information Technologies" has a special place compared to other subjects. According to B.S., the science of "Informatics and information technologies" is the basis of modern computers and software. "Informatics and information technologies" subjects "Starting to work with a text document", "Starting to work with images", "Starting to work with diagrams", "Starting to program", "Starting to work in search systems" are considered the main topics, and the students who have mastered the sections Necessary knowledge and skills are formed during supply creation. It is necessary to provide students with the necessary practical and theoretical knowledge in order to master these topics. In today's educational system, it is possible to use effective methods and methods to solve problems. One of the Bs is to organize the lesson process with an electronic manual created on the basis of software tools.

In this paragraph, when teaching the subjects of "Informatics and Information Technologies" to the students in "Informatics and Information Technologies" subject "Starting to work with a text document" to the students, first of all, information about the history of the origin, discovery, properties, questions, ways of representation, and the methods of the text. What is the difference between the methodology recommended in the current textbook and research?

Currently, in the 5th grade "Informatics and information technologies" textbook in general secondary schools of our Republic, this topic is given in the form of a short text in order to make it understandable to young children as follows:

In this module you will develop writing skills that will help you work on your final project. The final project will be about writing an article for the school magazine. In it you will learn:

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- basic skills of text processing;
- entering a text consisting of sentences and words into the document;
- using mouse buttons to mark and change the text in the document;
- Using some of the many commands available in Microsoft Word;
- save the document with the appropriate file name;

You will also learn:

- ensuring safety when using a computer;
- change the name of the saved document.

Before you begin, you should know the following:

- write simple sentences using spaces, periods and capital letters;
- what kind of device is the mouse;
- move the pointer on the computer screen by moving the mouse.

Word processing is the process of creating electronic documents by typing or modifying text in a document. Word processing is a very important skill to learn.

You can use this skill for many purposes, from completing schoolwork to landing your dream job.

Text processing skills are mainly used in the process of sending electronic documents to others via e-mail or other electronic means of communication.

Having these skills also means you can keep a copy of this document so you can change it whenever you want.

Microsoft Word is the word processing program used in this module. There are other word processing programs that you can use of any kind. These programs have many similar buttons and icons.

In addition to this information, the textbook provides young children with information on how to use a mouse, use a keyboard, select and edit text, delete text, copy text, print, save a file, check text, and practice using text and pictures to get started with text. .

Based on the goals and tasks set in the research, students' imagination skills were developed in the 5th grade "Informatics and Information Technologies" subject. In the electronic manual created on the basis of software tools, the topics related to this subject are presented in an animated form in a way that, unlike the current textbook, is comprehensible to the student and can be studied independently at home (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. View of the software package

When we refer to one of the buttons "Start working with a text document", "Start working with images", "Start working with diagrams", "Start programming" and "Start working with search engines" in the cover window in the image above, relevant information on the topics written in this button will be displayed. 'data window will open.

We can see an animation of this opening in the program when we make a reference to the first of the buttons given on the cover (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. A window to start working with a text document

The text document launch window also has several buttons, and these buttons are bordered by red outlines in Figure 2. In addition, back and forward buttons are installed at the bottom of the window. When the mouse pointer is pressed on the Word program icon located above these buttons, a window with brief information about the Microsoft Word program will open (see Figure 3).

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To write a word, the letters needed for that word are found on the keyboard and pressed in the required sequence. Each letter starts typing on the screen to form a word. Letters are also called symbols. When you type the first word to write a sentence, or when you type a single word, you can see that the first letter of the word is changed to a capital letter. Microsoft Word is usually configured to automatically capitalize the first letter of each sentence. Capitalize To change a letter to capitalization, press and hold the Shift key, then type the letter you want to capitalize. When you're done typing a letter, release the shift key.

Figure 3. Microsoft Word Program Options window

Word text editor is a text editor that works in the environment of the Windows system and serves to organize and print text documents with simple and complex structures. With the help of the Word text editor, any document can be prepared quickly and in a way that meets the requirements of the printing house. The Word text editor has the ability to perform all operations on texts as needed and includes all the requirements of modern computer technology.

The Word text editor will be indicated on the screen by the symbol "W" in "Microsoft office". It is started by pointing the mouse pointer to the "W" symbol and clicking the right mouse button. Then the Word text editor is loaded into the computer's memory and creates a new file called "Document 1" for entering simple structured texts. If you want to prepare a document with a complex structure (for example, a letter, fax, report, etc.), you can use the "Create" menu from the "File" menu. There are several complex structured document templates. You can choose the structured document template you need from them and prepare your document quickly and at a high level. The finished document is saved using one of the "Sokhranit" or "Sokhranit kak" commands of the "File" menu. Word saves all of your files with a ".doc" extension. To complete the work, the saved document is closed with the "Close" command of the "File" menu and the "Exit" command is clicked.

Below is an overview of the Word text editor window. The top row of the window is the title bar, which displays the icon and name of the text editor. In the rightmost part of this row, three small buttons are shown, which perform the functions of removing the window from the screen, resizing the

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window to the screen size, and closing the window, respectively. The second line of the window is the main menu bar of WORD, and each menu performs its own functions. In the next two lines of the window, there is an instrument panel, and they are represented by buttons with icons corresponding to their function. To find out their functions, it is enough to move the mouse pointer over the icons. The line after the toolbar is called the ruler and serves to expand and reduce the lines of the text part of the window.

When the next "PUSK" button is selected from the buttons shown in Figure 2 above, a window with the elements of the "PUSK" button opens on the screen.

You can use the "PUSK" menu if you want to perform an operation on a computer over the Windows operating system and with its help over the computer and its devices. If you click the push button with the left mouse button, the WINDOWS menu will open.

This menu consists of 8 sections:

- 1) using the "PROGRAMMY" section, we can see the list of programs installed on your computer and launch them;
- 2) using the "DOCUMENTY" section, you can see the list of the last used documents (mant, picture, music and other files) and restart them;
- 3) we can change and adjust the operating conditions of the Windows program and the characteristics of computer devices using the "SETTINGS" section;
- 4) File using the "NATY" section. We can search for a folder or a computer on the network;
- 5) we can see a set of questions and answers to them that appeared in the process of working in Windows with the help of the "SPRAVKA" command;
- 6) we can execute various programs or commands using the "VYPOLNIT" command;
- 7) we can end the user's session and start a new one using the "ZAVERSHENIE SESANSA" command;
- 8) We can shut down the computer using the ZAVERSHENIE RABOTY command.

If we select the "Perezagruzit" flag in the window that appears and press the OK button, the computer will restart. If Priostanovit selects the flag and clicks the OK button, the computer will stop working. If we select the flag "Turn off the computer" and press the OK button, the computer will start. Before turning off the computer, we need to close all open windows and running programs, because the computer needs to save the data in them.

When you press the button to enter the program, which is given in the window of starting work with the text document given above, the window of launching the program opens on the screen, and in this window it is also possible to perform the operation of entering text (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Microsoft Word program working window

When the switch button at the bottom of the above window is repeatedly pressed, information about the program's menus, text bolding, underlining text, formatting documents, choosing a test for evaluating students' knowledge on topics, solving the test, viewing the result windows are animated. are opened sequentially, this process can be viewed from the software tool.

Conclusions and suggestions. In conclusion, creating multimedia presentations on the basis of modern software tools and organizing lessons using them is one of the urgent issues in the teaching of the 5th grade "Informatics and Information Technologies" subject in general secondary schools.

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